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THE ROLE OF THE UPPER KARABAGH ECONOMIC DISTRICT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The Upper Karabakh economic region is one of the most productive regions of Azerbaijan in terms of tourism. The existing art and culture samples are an important factor in the development of tourism. Karabakh is an irreplaceable place for the development of both domestic and international tourism.

In order to turn tourism in this economic region into a profitable sector for the economy, first of all, the existing tourism potential must be assessed with a comprehensive and systematic approach, and the examples of material and cultural heritage in our countries must be clarified.

Currently, the State Tourism Agency is developing a tourism development strategy and policy for the liberated territories. In the near future, Upper Karabakh will introduce Azerbaijan to the world in the tourism sector and give a strong impetus to economic development.

Keywords: eco-tourism, tourism strategy, thermal tourism, tourism infrastructure, international tourism.

Tourism is one of the main directions of economic development. Unlike other areas, tourism, as a direction of economic development, has many advantages: investment in tourism pays off in a short period of time, invested capital has a high turnover ratio. Tourism, at the same time, is a field of service provided to a person, a factor that satisfies the need for recreation that meets his inner world, protects his health and promotes him to high culture.

Upper Karabakh economic region covers the city of Khankendi, Agdam, Jabrayil, Fuzuli, Khojavend, Khojaly, Shusha and Tartar regions. Upper Karabakh is located between the economic regions of Aran and Kalbajar-Lachin. There are 7 districts, 8 cities, and 8 settlements in the economic region. The total area of the economic district is 7248 km².

Here, due to the complexity of the terrain, there is a variety of climates: from mild warm climates with dry winters to cold climate types. The high peaks of the Murovdag range are sometimes covered with snow throughout the year. It is quite convenient for winter tourism. The region's forests, mountains, mineral springs, balneological climatic conditions, etc. opens opportunities for the development of the resort-health economy. There are balneological mountain-climate resorts and recreation areas in the economic district. In the mountain-climate resort that has been operating in Shusha for many years, the comfortable climate and

mineral waters made it possible for people to have effective treatment and relaxation.

There are many natural and anthropological monuments in the economic district. Upper Karabakh region is rich in historical and cultural monuments. There are architectural and archaeological monuments of world importance in the region. The tomb (19th century) in Khachin Turbali village of Agdam district, 11-arched (XI-XII) and 15-arched (13th century) Khudafarin bridges in Jabrayil district are famous. The world-important archaeological monuments include Azikh and Taglar caves in Fuzuli region (Paleolithic period), Chalagantape settlement (Eneolithic period) in Efatli village of Agdam district, Leylantepe settlement (Eneolithic period) in Guzanli settlement, Uzarliktepe settlement (Bronze period) in Agdam city, Borsunlu in Tartar district. Mounds (Bronze and First Iron Age), Khojaly Mounds (Bronze-Early Iron Age) in Khojaly District, Niftali Mounds (Bronze Age) in Khubyarli Village of Jabrayil District. The oldest Albanian temple in Khojavand region dates back to the IV-VI centuries (Susenlik village). There are many houses, palaces, castles, mosques, tombs (18th-19th centuries) of khans who lived in Shusha in the 18th century. There are many castles, mosques and other places of faith in the historical villages of Jabrayil, Fuzuli, Agdam regions. All this once again shows that the development of tourism in this economic region will be accelerated.

Since ancient times, the air of the city of Shusha, the Cidir plain, the water of the Isa spring, Turshsu, and Shirilan springs have been a salve for many diseases. Considering the curative properties of Shusha, modern sanatorium buildings and institutions can be built here in a short period of time.

It is not enough to list all the ancient architectural and artistic monuments that made Shusha famous. There are only officially registered 170 architectural monuments and 160 art monuments.

Shusha is called the "Conservatory of the East" - this city is the homeland of a number of outstanding musicians, great composers and conductors of Azerbaijan: Jabbar Garyagdi oglu, Gurban Pirimov, Bulbul, Seyid Shushinski, Khan Shushinski, Rashid Behbudov, Uzeyir Hajibeyov, Niyazi, Fikret Amirov, Suleyman Alasgarov. it belongs to celebrities.

Jabrayil is a human settlement that has existed not only in Azerbaijan, but all over the world since the ancient stone age. Azikh cave was once in the territory of Jabrayil district.

The territory of Jabrayil district is rich in material and cultural monuments. Among them, the "Divler Palace" cave located near the Dağtumas village, the "Mosque Hill", "Cangulu" and "Gumtepe" mounds in the Galacik village, the archaeological ones such as Mazannene and Marmar Nana tombs on the Diri mountain, "Başikesik Gumbaz" in the Doğtumas village, "Gala" in the Sirik village, "Giz Castle" on Diri mountain, Khudafar's bridges, Mosque complex in Chala-bilar village, "Sultan Majid bath" in the district center, "Round Tomb" in Shikhlar village, "Round" 8-cornered tombs and mausoleums in Khubyarli village, tombs and mausoleums in the Turkish cemetery each generation it is living history passed down from generation to generation. There are many written monuments in the territory of the region, of which the Orkhan written monument in Agoghlan is especially valuable. [1.p.347]

Khudafarin bridge, which is considered as a symbol of Azerbaijan, is also located in Jabrayil district. The first information about this bridge dates back to the VIII-IX centuries. Khudafar's bridge was built on the caravan route connecting the medieval cities of South Azerbaijan and North Azerbaijan. It also has important military-strategic importance. The first bridge built in the narrowest part of the Araz river, surrounded by rocks, operated from the end of the 8th century to the beginning of the 9th century until the 19th century. The brick bridge was built in the 12th century.

Jabrayil has a wide potential in terms of tourism. Since Jabrayil covers both lowland, foothills and mountainous areas, it has wide opportunities for the development of tourism.

There are many ancient architectural monuments in the territory of Aghdam region. Caravanserai in Shahbulag village (XVIII century), Khanoghlan mausoleum (XVII century), mosque (XVII century), palace and mausoleum of Panahali Khan, "Gutlu Musa oglu" mausoleum (XIV century) in Khachintürbatli village, two mausoleums and a mosque in Papavand village, Boz Dağın Chapilim cave temple in the northern foothills, Caucasian German temples belonging to the

Christian era are of this type. There is an unusual museum in Aghdam - Bread Museum. Here, unique exponents - archaeological findings related to bread and grain growing have been collected. Among the exponents there are grains turned into stone, hand mills, dishes, ancient books, manuscripts, various materials that talk about the development of grain farming, agricultural tools (sickle, gravel, grain threshing rod, etc.). Many historical monuments were destroyed as a result of Armenian military aggression. 89 villages in Aghdam region were completely destroyed and razed to the ground with unprecedented cruelty in the history of mankind. The location of Aghdam is very important for the development of Azerbaijani tourism.

Although the main tourism potential of Karabakh is concentrated in Shusha and Aghdam, all regions of the region are suitable for treatment and recreation.

Fuzuli covers sloping plains and lowlands from the south-eastern foothills of the Karabakh mountain range to the Araz river. It borders with Iran along Jabrayil, Khojavand, Agjabadi, Beylagan regions and Araz river. Fuzuli region, where the Azikh cave, one of the oldest settlements, is located, is also distinguished by its favorable nature and charming landscape. This means new opportunities for the interior, including the arrival style.

Fuzuli region is rich in historical and religious monuments, especially tombs. These monuments include the octagonal tomb of Sheikh Babı Yaqub (13th century) located in Babı village of the region, the Mirali tomb of the 14th century in the village of Aşağı Veysalli, the tomb on the chest-shaped tombstone in the area of the medieval cemetery in the village of Ahmadalılar, and the Jalil tomb, which is said to belong to the 19th century.

Khudafarin bridge, Azikh cave may become a tourist route in the future. Although our cultural and historical monuments were destroyed, it will be possible to organize tours to those destinations after their restoration.

Some indicators related to tourism in Tartar region can be mentioned. The number of hotels and hotel-type establishments in Tarter district is 15.

Although great work has been done in the direction of tourism development in Azerbaijan in recent years, Karabakh and its surrounding regions, which have the greatest tourism potential of our country, were left out of these processes due to the fact that they were occupied until now. This land, which impresses guests with its charming nature in the four seasons, is an epic in languages with its pure air, healing waters, and historical monuments, has already been freed from the enemy. One of the main topics discussed today is the development of tourism in our territories freed from occupation.

The occupation of Karabakh has led Azerbaijan to face not only territorial, but also a number of economic, social and cultural losses. We should include financial and moral losses in the field of tourism among those problems.

It is known that Upper Karabakh is one of the historical places of Azerbaijan, and it is also a land distinguished by its beautiful and irreplaceable nature. The

natural beauty of the occupied lands can turn the Upper Karabakh economic region into a destination for tourists from around the world.

These tourism and treatment facilities will introduce the national-historical values of the Azerbaijani people to the world and bring enough income to the state budget. As in other parts of our country, more tourist facilities will be built here using the opportunities provided by our independence.

After the security, which is the main factor in our lands freed from occupation, is fully ensured, visits for the purpose of visiting will be organized first, and then after the creation of the appropriate infrastructure, including tourism infrastructure, and the provision of accommodation, the trips for the purpose of recreation will be organized.

In order to develop tourism in Upper Karabakh, the existing tourism potential should be evaluated with a complex and systematic approach, and the examples of material and cultural heritage in our lands should be clarified. Among the works to be done in this direction, it is envisaged to create new tourism routes, to prepare guides who are knowledgeable about the tourism potential of Upper Karabakh, and finally to carry out large-scale propaganda work to attract foreign tourists to Upper Karabakh.

It is possible to develop various types of tourism in the Upper Karabakh economic region. For example, there are conditions for the development of eco-tourism. Along with international hotels, two-star and multi-star hotels should be built. Tourism development is expected in those areas. [2]

Karabakh horses are famous in the world. Separate excursions can be arranged for these horses.

Upper Karabakh economic region is rich in natural resources. Those places have quite rich water resources. There are fertile conditions for the development of thermal tourism in those areas. Infrastructure should be created in those areas, including tourism infrastructure. By working in various directions and doing complex works, Upper Karabakh can be quickly turned into a tourist destination.

The organization of religious tours in the economic district will be interesting for tourists from the point of view of studying spiritual values. The peculiarity of the mosques in Karabakh is that they are carriers of Aran culture. In the construction of those mosques, very beautiful examples of carvings were created using local construction materials. There are dozens and hundreds of tombs with underground and above ground parts in the liberated territories.

In addition, it is possible to organize carpet tours in Karabakh. Carpets woven in Karabakh are not woven anywhere in the world.

There is great potential for the construction of ropeways in our liberated territories. The uniqueness of these regions is that these areas have favorable opportunities for religious, ecological, agro-tourism, as well as other types of tourism.

Tourism has a positive effect on the country's economy when tourism develops comprehensively in connection with other areas of the economy. In other words, tourism is economically efficient when developed in parallel with other socio-economic complexes. The development of tourism requires the construction and modernization of hotels, airports, the construction of roads, the improvement of cities and villages, the restoration and protection of historical and architectural monuments. Thus, the development of tourism in the Upper Karabakh economic region will affect the development of automobiles, food, textiles, shoes and other fields, in addition to the fields to which it is traditionally related. [3.p.115]

Currently, the State Tourism Agency is preparing the tourism development strategy and policy of the liberated territories. The development of tourism products will be carried out in parallel with the construction of tourism infrastructure in those areas. Another issue is attracting investments to this region. Initially, it is envisaged to create transport infrastructure, civil infrastructure and conditions for investments.

In general, Upper Karabakh is the region of Azerbaijan with the richest tourism potential. Here, art, ancient history and culture, fascinating natural examples are suitable for creating a tourist complex. In order to free the territory from occupation, special projects related to tourism will be implemented for the purpose of socio-economic development of those territories as a whole. This will affect the transformation of the tourism sector into one of the most profitable sectors in Azerbaijan and the strengthening of the economy.

Summary: Upper Karabakh economic region is one of the most efficient regions of Azerbaijan from the point of view of tourism. The art and culture examples available here are an important factor for the development of tourism. Karabakh is an irreplaceable place for the development of both domestic and international tourism.

In order to turn tourism into a profitable area for the economy in this economic region, first of all, the existing tourism potential should be evaluated with a complex and systematic approach, and the examples of material and cultural heritage in our lands should be clarified.

Currently, the State Tourism Agency is preparing the tourism development strategy and policy of the liberated territories. In the near future, Upper Karabakh will introduce Azerbaijan to the whole world in the tourism sector and give a strong impetus to the development of the economy.

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